

Christianity in Alexandria: From Origen to Athanasius

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Entry tags: Christianity, Early Christianity, Neoplatonism, Religious Group, Orthodox/Eastern Christian, Orthodoxy, Christian Traditions, Orthodoxy

The tradition of the Orthodox Church attributes the foundation of the Church of Alexandria to Mark, the author of the Gospel. Christianity, however, probably entered Alexandria through its large Jewish community. Clear evidence of an organized Alexandrian church appears around 180 CE, although its origins must be much earlier, with a bishop and twelve presbyters. Public preaching was hardly possible where Christianity was not a legal religion, and a key to Christian expansion lay in its teachers, resembling those of a philosophical school. The Catechetical school of Alexandria not only prepared enquirers for baptism, but also presented Christianity in terms of the Greek intellectual tradition. Successive leaders of the school were Pantaeus, a converted Stoic philosopher, Clement, also a converted philosopher, of Athenian origin, and Origen, born of Christian parents around 185, who studied under Ammonius Saccas. In Alexandria, during the period under investigation, Christianity became quite different in the Catechetical School of the city. Clement saw philosophy as part of a divine educational process to prepare humanity for Christianity and the Christian life as a school of perfection. He accepted the Apostolic traditions, but he wished to show that they possessed a far deeper meaning than they could possibly have possessed among the immediate followers of Christ. Clement was convinced that this new religion, Christianity, if properly understood, was worthy of being accepted by the most enlightened minds. He claimed the most perfect freedom of interpretation and speculation. By applying the same allegorical interpretation which Philo had used in interpreting the Old Testament, to the New, Clement convinced himself and managed to convince others that there was no opposition between philosophy and religion. What Clement had most at heart was not the letter but the spirit, not the historical events, but their deeper meaning in universal history. Origen was the most prodigious scholar of early Christianity. He introduced new forms of learned activity such as textual criticism and systematic theology, extending others such as the biblical commentary, and engaging with the whole range of Greek thought and science. Like Clement he drew on the Platonism already used by the Alexandrian Jewish scholar Philo to present biblical teaching, and, like Philo, used allegorical exegesis of the Old Testament, maintaining the link between Christianity and Israel. Up to 313, Alexandrian Christianity suffered periodic violence, sometimes severe, from the Roman state. However, with the toleration of Christianity in 313, the first major theological controversy arose. The Alexandrian presbyter Arius posited a theory of the divine "sonship" which could be interpreted as making Jesus Christ a sort of demigod. Denounced by his bishop, Alexander, Arius found support elsewhere in the Greek world. The creed of the Council of Nicaea (325 CE) established the position generally regarded as orthodox, which was elaborated by the Alexandrian theologian and future bishop Athanasius (295-373). Both sides could claim to be drawing on Origen's legacy. Alexandrian theology continued to focus on the full divinity of Christ, and on the union of the divine and human in Christ, an emphasis later visible when a majority in the Egyptian church adopted a Monophysite form of theology.

Date Range: 185 CE - 373 CE

Region: The city of Alexandria

Region tags: Africa, Eastern Mediterranean, Egypt, Alexandria (Egypt)

The city of Alexandria

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: P. M. Fraser, *Ptolemaic Alexandria* (1972)
- Source 2: A. Bernand, *Alexandrie la Grande* (1966)
- Source 3: Judith McKenzie et al., *The Architecture of Alexandria and Egypt, 300 B.C.–A.D. 700*. (Pelican History of Art, Yale University Press, 2007)
- Source 1: Haas Christopher, *Alexandria in Late Antiquity: Topography and Social Conflict*, Johns Hopkins University Press: Baltimore 1997

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://www.alexandria.gov.eg/Alex/english/Christianity.html>
- Source 1 Description: Alexandria and Christianity
- Source 2 URL: <https://pcma.uw.edu.pl/en/2019/04/28/alexandria-kom-el-dikka/>
- Source 2 Description: Alexandria, Kom el-Dikka
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.ancientportsantiques.com/a-few-ports/alexandria-pharos-island/>
- Source 3 Description: Alexandria Pharos island

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=hvd.hxj9mv&view=1up&seq=56>
- Source 1 Description: Carsten Niebuhr (1792). "Of the City of Alexandria". *Travels through Arabia*. Translated by Robert Heron.

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Are they written:

– Yes

Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– No

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Origen got involved in the codification of the biblical canon. His canon included all of the books in the current New Testament canon except for four books: James, 2nd Peter, and the 2nd and 3rd epistles of John. He also included the "Shepherd" of Hermas which was later rejected. In his Easter letter of 367, Patriarch Athanasius of Alexandria gave a list of exactly the same books that would become the New Testament–27 book–proto-canon, and used the phrase "being canonized".

Reference: Gamble, Harry. *The New Testament Canon: Its Making and Meaning*. Eugene, Oregon: Wipf & Stock Publishers, 2002.

Reference: Metzger, Bruce. *The Canon of the New Testament: Its Origin, Development, and Significance*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1997.

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: A Christian text known as the Epistle of Barnabas, dated between 70 CE and 138 CE, is probably Alexandrian reflects intense controversy between Christians and traditional Jews over the right use of Scripture; the author may himself have been Jewish. Fragments of an early Gospel, otherwise unknown, have been found in Egypt, but the first named Egyptian Christian writers (all using Greek) belong to the Gnostic wing of Christianity, which produced a radically Hellenistic interpretation of the Christian message, distancing it from the synagogue. There are also works of Gnostic tendency, purporting to represent the words of Jesus, most notably the Gospel of Thomas, found in Coptic translation. None of these works necessarily represents the ethos of Alexandrian Christianity of the period under consideration as a whole, but they do reflect the intellectual challenges that the Greek tradition in Alexandria presented for Christianity, and perhaps a reaction against an earlier period when Christianity was presented in essentially Jewish terms.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Field doesn't know

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 300

Reference: Delia, Diana. "The Population of Roman Alexandria". *Transactions of the American Philological Association* 118 (1988): 275–92.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Victory columns, carious gates that led to the city.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Bishop Dionysius of Alexandria (248 CE - 264 CE) undertook missionary activities with non-Christians living at the region near Alexandria.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: During 249, a major persecution was carried out in Alexandria by a polytheist mob, and hundreds of Christians were assaulted, stoned, burned or cut down on account of their refusal to deny their faith. In January 250 CE the new emperor Decius issued a decree of legal persecution. Out of fear many Christians denied their faith by offering a token polytheist sacrifice, while others attempted to obtain false documents affirming their sacrifice. Others who refused to sacrifice faced public ridicule and shame among their family and friends, and, if found by the authorities, brutal torture and execution. Many fled from the city into the desert, where most succumbed to exposure, hunger, thirst, or attacks by bandits or wild animals. With the Edict of Milan in 313, Christians would be benevolently treated within the Roman Empire.

Is iconography present:

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

Notes: Arius, for example, the notorious Alexandrian heretic, may have been poisoned by his opponents. Yet, some of his contemporaries asserted that the circumstances of his death were a miraculous consequence of his heretical views. The latter view was evident in the account of Arius's death by a bitter enemy, Socrates Scholasticus: It was then Saturday, and Arius was expecting to assemble with the church on the day following: but divine retribution overtook his daring criminalities. For going out of the imperial palace, attended by a crowd of Eusebian partisans like guards, he paraded proudly through the midst of the city, attracting the notice of all the people. As he approached the place called Constantine's Forum, where the column of porphyry is erected, a terror arising from the remorse of conscience seized Arius, and with the terror a violent relaxation of the bowels: he therefore enquired whether there was a convenient place near, and being directed to the back of Constantine's Forum, he hastened thither. Soon after a faintness came over him, and together with the evacuations his bowels protruded, followed by a copious hemorrhage, and the descent of the smaller intestines: moreover portions of his spleen and liver were brought off in the effusion of blood, so that he almost immediately died. The scene of this catastrophe still is shown at Constantinople, as I have said, behind the

shambles in the colonnade: and by persons going by pointing the finger at the place, there is a perpetual remembrance preserved of this extraordinary kind of death

Reference: Kirsch, Jonathan. *God Against the Gods : The History of the War Between Monotheism and Polytheism*. New York: Viking Compass, 2004.

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:
– Yes

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:
– Yes

↳ Punished in the afterlife:
– Yes

↳ Cursed by "high god":
– Yes

↳ Cursed by other supernatural being(s):
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other divine punishment:
– No

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (with smaller religious groups not officially allowed but in practice tolerated)

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: During the episcopate of Patriarch Alexander (312-328) a systematic program of church building begun. Alexander oversaw the construction of two important churches: the church of Saint Theonas and the church dedicated to the archangel Michael, which was originally the temple of Kronos (or Saturn), a

shrine attested as early as the Ptolemaic period.

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– No

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– Yes

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– Yes

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– No

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– Yes

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

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Notes: A Christian text known as the Epistle of Barnabas, dated between 70 CE and 138 CE, is probably Alexandrian reflects intense controversy between Christians and traditional Jews over the right use of Scripture; the author may himself have been Jewish. Fragments of an early Gospel, otherwise unknown, have been found in Egypt, but the first named Egyptian Christian writers (all using Greek) belong to the Gnostic wing of Christianity, which produced a radically Hellenistic interpretation of the Christian message, distancing it from the synagogue. There are also works of Gnostic tendency, purporting to represent the words of Jesus, most notably the Gospel of Thomas, found in Coptic translation. None of these works necessarily represents the ethos of Alexandrian Christianity of the period under consideration as a whole, but they do reflect the intellectual challenges that the Greek tradition in Alexandria presented for Christianity, and perhaps a reaction against an earlier period when Christianity was presented in essentially Jewish terms.

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↳ Punished in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Cursed by "high god":

– Yes

↳ Cursed by other supernatural being(s):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other divine punishment:

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Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 300

Reference: Delia, Diana. "The Population of Roman Alexandria". *Transactions of the American Philological Association* 118 (1988): 275–92.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

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Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (with smaller religious groups not officially allowed but in practice tolerated)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

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↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

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↳ A single leader of a local community:

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↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:
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Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:
– Yes

↳ Are they oral:
– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:
– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

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↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

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Notes: Origen got involved in the codification of the biblical canon. His canon included all of the books in the current New Testament canon except for four books: James, 2nd Peter, and

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Reference: Metzger, Bruce. *The Canon of the New Testament: Its Origin, Development, and Significance*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1997.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:
– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:
– Yes

↳ Temples:
– Yes

↳ Altars:
– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:
– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:
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↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:
– Yes [specify]: Victory columns, carious gates that led to the city.

Is iconography present:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: During the episcopate of Patriarch Alexander (312-328) a systematic program of church building begun. Alexander oversaw the construction of two important churches: the church of Saint Theonas and the church dedicated to the archangel Michael, which was originally the temple of Kronos (or Saturn), a shrine attested as early as the Ptolemaic period.

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– No

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Reference: Novenson, Matthew . "The Fate of Messiah Christology in Early Christianity". In *The Grammar of Messianism: An Ancient Jewish Political Idiom and Its Users* the Grammar of Messianism: An Ancient Jewish Political Idiom and Its Users. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2017.

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– No

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:
– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: Origen developed a key concept for Christian theology, the restoration of all things (apokatastasis) to their original state of creation. The idea of the restoration of all things was a deeply integrated element

of Alexandrian systematic theology and had important implications for Christian soteriology. Origen saw salvation as the reformation of all fallen beings in the image of Logos (Jesus Christ), who is the image of God. In particular, three motifs are central to Origen's soteriology, punishment, healing and training. With these, God through the Logos leads the rational beings back to the original state of creation, by which the eschatological completion is a return to the beginning, which in turn is completed by this perfection.

Reference: Jacobsen, Anders-Christian . "Eschatology in Origen from Alexandria". In *Eschatology in Antiquity*. London: Routledge, 2021.

- ↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:
 - Yes
- ↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:
 - No
- ↳ Eschaton at some other time:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:
 - Yes
- ↳ Divine judgment event:
 - Yes
- ↳ Restoration of the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Establishment of a new political system:
 - No

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Courage (generic):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - No
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - No
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - No
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - Yes

- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - No

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.
Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - No
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - No
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Reference: Novenson, Matthew . "The Fate of Messiah Christology in Early Christianity". In *The Grammar of Messianism: An Ancient Jewish Political Idiom and Its Users* the Grammar of Messianism: An Ancient Jewish Political Idiom and Its Users. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2017.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: Origen developed a key concept for Christian theology, the restoration of all things (apokatastasis) to their original state of creation. The idea of the restoration of all things was a deeply integrated element of Alexandrian systematic theology and had important implications for Christian soteriology. Origen saw salvation as the reformation of all fallen beings in the image of Logos (Jesus Christ), who is the image of God. In particular, three motifs are central to Origen's soteriology, punishment, healing and training. With these, God through the Logos leads the rational beings back to the original state of creation, by which the eschatological completion is a return to the beginning, which in turn is completed by this perfection.

Reference: Jacobsen, Anders-Christian . "Eschatology in Origen from Alexandria". In *Eschatology in Antiquity*. London: Routledge, 2021.

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

- ↳ Eschaton at some other time:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:
 - Yes
- ↳ Divine judgment event:
 - Yes
- ↳ Restoration of the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Establishment of a new political system:
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of a new religious system:
 - No
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:
 - No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

- ↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):
– Field doesn't know

↳ Courage (generic):
– Field doesn't know

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:
– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Cooperation:

- Field doesn't know
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
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 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
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- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
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- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
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- ↳ Strength (physical):
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- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - No
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
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- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: However, the Church historian Eusebius of Caesarea says that Origen had himself castrated, an act known as an orchiectomy. Origen devoted himself to study and self-denial. When he was continually plagued by lust for women, he decided to castrate himself, in order to avoid the temptation.

Reference: Caner, Daniel . "The Practice and Prohibition of Self-castration in Early Christianity". *Vigiliae*

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: However, the Church historian Eusebius of Caesarea says that Origen had himself castrated, an act known as an orchietomy. Origen devoted himself to study and self-denial. When he was continually plagued by lust for women, he decided to castrate himself, in order to avoid the temptation.

Reference: Caner, Daniel . "The Practice and Prohibition of Self-castration in Early Christianity". *Vigiliae Christianae* 51, no. 4 (1997): 396–415. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2307/1583869>.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:
I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: The School of Alexandria started as a Catechetical School, where candidates were admitted to learn the Christian faith and some Biblical studies to qualify for baptism. Its teaching was encyclopedic; first presenting the whole series of profane sciences, and then rising to moral and religious philosophy, and finally to Christian theology, as set forth in the form of commentaries on the sacred books. This encyclopedic conception of teaching was an Alexandrian tradition, for it was also found in Alexandrian pagan and Jewish schools. Worship went side by side with study in the School. Teachers and their students practiced prayer, fasting and diverse ways of asceticism. In addition to continence in food and drink, they were also continent in earthly possessions. In purity and integrity their lives were exemplary. Celibacy was a recommended ideal.

Reference: Ranson , Guy Harvey . The Anthropology of the Catechetical School of Alexandria. Louisville, KY: Southern Baptist Theological Seminary, 1944.

Reference: Ellens, J. Harold. The Ancient Library of Alexandria and Early Christian Theological Development. Ann Arbor, Michigan: Institute for Antiquity and Christianity, 2009.

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– Yes

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Long before the establishment of Christianity in Alexandria, the city was famous for its many schools, the largest of which was the "Museum," founded by Ptolemy and became the most famous school in the East. In addition, there were the "Serapeum" and the "Sebastion." Each of these three schools had its own huge library. The Museum, as its name proclaims, was dedicated to the Muses, and was a sort of university in which the most distinguished writers, scientists, and philosophers gathered

and worked. Largely because of these institutions, Alexandria soon became famous as a rich center of knowledge. Numerous Jewish schools were also scattered everywhere.

Reference: MacLeod, Roy. *The Library of Alexandria: Centre of Learning in the Ancient World*. London, New York: I.B. Tauris, 2004.

Reference: Canfora, Luciano. *The Vanished Library: A Wonder of the Ancient World*. Stanford, California: University of California Press, 1990.

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than

the religious group in question:

– Yes

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

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– Yes

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encyclopedic conception of teaching was an Alexandrian tradition, for it was also found in Alexandrian pagan and Jewish schools. Worship went side by side with study in the School. Teachers and their students practiced prayer, fasting and diverse ways of asceticism. In addition to continence in food and drink, they were also continent in earthly possessions. In purity and integrity their lives were exemplary. Celibacy was a recommended ideal.

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Reference: Canfora , Luciano . The Vanished Library: A Wonder of the Ancient World. Stanford, California: University of California Press, 1990.

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Field doesn't know

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Field doesn't know

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Field doesn't know

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Field doesn't know

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

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